

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 25th December 2022

Accepted: 04th January 2023

Online: 05th January 2023

KEY WORDS

RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND CHINA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7505354>

ABSTRACT

All of us know that China is one of the most developed countries in the world according to any fields, in science, in industry, in economics, in development and so on. What is development? What is industry and science? Yes, when we think about the questions above, the thought of China creeps in our mind. That is why we can freely say that there are so many reasons which urge us on learning about China and its relations with Central Asia countries, especially, with Uzbekistan.

Industrious, courageous, faithful and responsible nations of China and Uzbekistan have similar opinions about family, motherland and life. Uzbekistan is a developing country which has been having a good and lasting relationship with China since ancient times because of Great Silk Road. But the first Chinese ambassador, Zhang Xiang, arrival in Davan state (Fergana). It happened in the year 128BC. This event can be considered the beginning of diplomatic relations between the two countries. During the Ming Dynasty, which came to power in 1368, the relations between China and Turkestan, which were carried out through the Great Silk Road, weakened a little. But during the period of Timurids, these relations were revived again. Since 1950, Uzbekistan provided great assistance to Xingjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region in training personnel, providing local population with literature and textbooks in Uyghur and Kazakh languages, providing medical assistance, identifying underground resources, and improving the irrigation system. ¹

Coming to now, stable, scientific, commercial, humanitarian relations between nations are serving to strengthen the interactions of these two countries. Uzbekistan considers the leader country – the Republic of China as a reliable and close partner. Interrelations are based on mutual respect and strong friendship. In the last years the friendship and strategic cooperation of Uzbekistan and China moved to next stage due to the political power and joint attempts of the leaders of two countries. For example, the cooperation in education as in every field is rapidly developing. There are lots of training courses between students, practitioners and ministries. In the field of tourism, in 2009, a memorandum was signed between Uzbek tourism and the Chinese National Tourism Administration. Since 2010, the

¹ https://uz.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/O%CA%BBzbekiston_%E2%80%94_Xitoy_Xalq_Respublikasi_munosabatlari

first practical actions on the issue of providing group travel status to Uzbekistan have begun. The cooperation between Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages (SSIF) and the University of Foreign languages in Shanghai informs how much these two countries care about their scientific interactions. Every year scientific forums on the theme “Languages, education and culture” are traditionally held. Today Chinese lessons are being taught at the faculty of Philology and teaching languages of SSIF. Two hundred and ninety three bachelor students are learning Chinese in that institute. Apart from that Chinese language is being taught as a second language in SSIF and two hundred and twenty two students are learning. There is also the chair of Eastern Languages and in this division fifteen native Chinese teachers work. In 2014 Confucius Institute was formed in the presence of SSIF. The main aim of this is that contributing to developing the economic, cultural relations between Uzbekistan and China by spreading Chinese language and literature among youngsters. Not only teaching is their intention, but also they plan to hold cultural meetings. Confucius Institute helps to provide Chinese enterprises and factories situated in Uzbekistan with experts and trained personnel. At the same time in the university of Foreign languages in China Uzbek language is being taught. Now we are living in fast-paced life so I think it is the demand of the world to communicate and cooperate with developed countries, especially, in the branch of science.

Diplomatic relations between Uzbekistan and China. In 1991, China recognized the independence of Uzbekistan. It has been thirty years since diplomatic relations of the two countries established in 1992, 2th January. On October 15, 1992, the embassy of China was opened in Tashkent, and on May 6, 1995, the embassy of Uzbekistan was opened in Beijing. China continues to cooperate with Uzbekistan according to the project of “The economic belt of Great Silk Road” which is related to Central Asia. In a short time, “The belt and Road” free trading global project has become one of the most important initiative, as well as free and prosperous trade relations among Asian, European, and African countries, along with, important in the domestic economic development of joint states. In terms of economy, China is a large new trade partner of the majority countries in the universe, the basis of machinery importer, an investor for up to date infrastructure. ²In 2017, 12th May the visit of the president of Uzbekistan, Sh.Mirziyoyev, to China started an absolutely new stage of mutual friendship. In this meeting more than one hundred documents were signed. Generally, cooperation relations between the governments, ministries and departments of Uzbekistan and China, as well as research scientists, have been widely established. Chinese scholars take into consideration learning about the modern politics and economic progress of Uzbekistan. Particularly, they are interested in the political activity and reforms of president Sh.Mirziyoyev. For instance, in 2019 December, the book named “President Sh.Mirziyoyev – the architect of the reforms’ period of Uzbekistan” was published. We can also see that Chinese art representatives’ interests in Uzbek culture and art. In order to prove it we can take as an example the statue of great artist, famous miniaturist Kamaliddin Bekhzad which was erected in 2003 in Changchung, China. In 2017 the statue of a great thinker, Alisher Navai, was built in the University of Shanghai.

² Komolitdinova Kholishxon and Lv JianPing, “The opportunities for bilateral cooperation between China and Uzbekistan in the lens of Belt and Road”, October 2020 International Journal of Economics and Finance, page 43

Trade between the two countries. It is obvious that the reasons for extending relations are economic fields and trade. It has been reported that China accounts for 16.8 percent of Uzbekistan external commercial turnover. The exports of Uzbekistan to China are growing up. The exports comprise natural gas, uranium, copper, cotton, mineral fertilizer. It is possible to observe the increase of goods of China in the markets of Uzbekistan. Equipment, electronics, electrical equipment, coffee, consumer goods, tea and spices, optical equipment and devices, vehicles, textile products, clothes, shoes are imported from China. Uzbekistan supplies precious metals and products made from them, mineral fuel, oil and oil products, cotton and silk fiber, plastic and etc. to China. According to the contract of natural gas which was signed in 2011 providing China with gas was planned for 25 years. In 2020 October, Uzbekistan opened a head consulate for widening trading relations. It was second consular office in China because initial one is active in Shanghai. According to the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2010 bilateral trade reached \$2085.3 million, of which \$899.9 million was export and \$1185.4 million was import. A total of 347 Chinese-invested enterprises are operating in Uzbekistan, 57 of which were established with 100 % Chinese capital. Sixty four Chinese companies were accredited by the Ministry of Foreign Economic Relations and Trade. The main areas of economic cooperation are bilateral trade, light industry, processing of agricultural products, and information technologies.

As noted, the People's Republic of China is one of the main trade and economic partners of Uzbekistan, and the roots of mutual economic, social and cultural relations between the two countries go back to the ancient past. Even today, mutually beneficial cooperation relations are developing between the two countries on the basis of high trust and strong friendly relations. The scope of bilateral cooperation between the countries, as well as within the framework of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, "One Place – One Road" program, is expanding and reaching a new level of quality.

In 2017, Sun Litze, Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of the People's Republic of China to Uzbekistan, said in an interview with UzReport AA reporter: First of all, I would like to congratulate all the Uzbek people on the arrival of Navruz. Uzbekistan is a large powerful country in Central Asia. China always views relations with Uzbekistan from a strategic and perspective point of view. After the independence of Uzbekistan, China was the first to establish diplomatic relations with it. China-Uzbekistan relations, which have stood the test of time for 25 years and have withstood risks in the international arena, continue to develop steadily. The parties have been actively cooperating in all spheres, firmly supporting each other in issues related to the vital interests of both countries.³ In conclusion, it should be noted that in recent years, relations between the republic of Uzbekistan and the republic of China have risen to a new level in terms of quality, and this indicates that the two countries are long-term strategic partners. This fully corresponds to the interests of the people of the two countries and the requirements of the present time.

³<http://www.uzbekistan-geneva.ch/buyuk-ipak-yo-lida-joylashgan-o-zbekiston-va-xitoy-diplomatik.html>